

Comparison of Rocuronium and Succinylcholine for Rapid Sequence Intubation in the Emergency Department: A Cross-sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Rapid Sequence Intubation (RSI) is an essential technique in emergency care, requiring the use of neuromuscular blocking agents to secure the airway efficiently. While Succinylcholine has long been the standard choice, Rocuronium has gained recognition as a suitable alternative, largely due to its advantageous safety characteristics.

Methods: An observational cross-sectional study was conducted on 86 adult patients requiring emergency tracheal intubation. Patients were divided equally into two groups: one receiving Succinylcholine and the other Rocuronium. Key parameters evaluated included intubation success rate, intubation conditions (using the Copenhagen Score), number of attempts, complications, and patient vitals.

Results: Both groups showed comparable demographic characteristics and clinical conditions. No statistically significant differences were found in intubation success rates, complications (hypotension, hypertension, desaturation), or additional medication use ($p > 0.05$). However, the Succinylcholine group demonstrated slightly better intubation conditions and a higher rate of first attempt success.

Conclusion: Both Succinylcholine and Rocuronium have been shown to be safe and effective options for performing Rapid Sequence Intubation in emergency situations. While Succinylcholine showed marginally superior intubation conditions, Rocuronium remains a suitable alternative, especially when contraindications to Succinylcholine exist.

Keywords: Rapid Sequence Intubation, Succinylcholine, Rocuronium, Emergency Department, Airway Management, Neuromuscular Blocking Agents.

Introduction

In emergency settings, securing the airway through tracheal intubation is a critical intervention¹, and the use of sedation significantly enhances both its safety and effectiveness². For patients requiring emergency airway management, rapid sequence intubation (RSI) is the preferred approach³. RSI involves the swift delivery of a sedative along with a muscle relaxant². By using a neuromuscular blocking medication, the intubation circumstances are improved and the chances of a successful and the chances of a successful initial attempt are increased⁴. Intravenous induction using such agents is considered ideal in the Emergency Department environment^{5,6}. Succinylcholine is commonly used as the neuromuscular blocker of choice⁷, though it comes with several side effects and contraindications².

Research has indicated that rocuronium, due to its similar pharmacokinetics, can match succinylcholine in onset time and may serve as a viable alternative in emergency scenarios⁹. Additionally, aside from potential allergic reactions, rocuronium has fewer adverse effects and contraindications, including a lower tendency to cause rapid oxygen desaturation, increased oxygen use, or hyperkalemia compared to succinylcholine^{8,10}. Furthermore, patients generally tolerate rocuronium better than succinylcholine²

Succinylcholine, a depolarizing muscle relaxant, produces quick muscle paralysis by causing initial muscle twitching followed by relaxation¹¹. Rocuronium, in contrast, is a non-depolarizing agent that takes about 2 to 3 minutes to take effect and works by competitively inhibiting transmission at the neuromuscular junction^{12,13}. Its effects can also be reversed with sugammadex⁵.

Rocuronium usage has significantly increased in emergency department ¹⁴. Despite the fact that succinylcholine has been established in multiple clinical trials to improve intubation conditions ^{7,15}, a retrospective analysis showed that rocuronium, is equally effective as succinylcholine for first-attempt intubation in emergencies when administered at doses greater than 1 mg/kg¹⁶. Many of the comparisons between these two agents have taken place in controlled operating room environments ^{17,18}, however, only a small number of clinical trials¹⁹, observational studies ¹⁴, prospective studies ²⁰, and retrospective analyses¹⁶ concentrated on out-of-hospital settings, where the risk of aspiration must be minimized ²¹.

One randomized controlled trial ² found rocuronium to be less effective than succinylcholine for intubation, while other studies—including another randomized trial ¹⁹, observational ¹⁴, prospective ²⁰, and retrospective ¹⁶ research—suggest they perform equally well. The best neuromuscular blocking agent to use in out-of-hospital situations is still unknown due to this contradicting data. A cross-sectional study comparing the effectiveness of rocuronium and succinylcholine in rapid sequence intubation in the emergency department was undertaken at a single centre in the Nims hospital in Rajasthan, Jaipur, in order to answer this issue.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population

- Period: December 2024 – May 2025
- Setting: Nims Hospital Rajasthan , Jaipur
- Design: Cross-sectional observational study
- Sample size: 86 (43 per group)

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age >18 years
2. Required emergency tracheal intubation
3. Reasons including poor GCS, trauma, COPD, respiratory failure

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnant females
2. Age <18 years
3. Cardiac arrest
4. Allergy to rocuronium/succinylcholine

Methodology

Patients admitted to the emergency department were selected based on inclusion/exclusion criteria. A thorough history and clinical examination were conducted, followed by completion of a clinical perma documenting examination findings and investigations.

Airway assessment utilized the **L.E.M.O.N.** mnemonic:

- **L** – Look from outside
- **E** – Evaluate 3-3-2 rule
- **M** – Mallampati score
- **O** – Obstruction/Obesity
- **N** – Neck mobility

Intervention Protocol

Prior to induction, all patients received standardized preoxygenation. Patients were allocated to one of two intervention groups:

Succinylcholine Group (SY): Patients (n=43) received succinylcholine at 1 mg/kg IV.

Rocuronium Group (RM): Patients (n=43) received rocuronium at 1.2 mg/kg IV.

All patients received an induction agent (ketamine 2 mg/kg, etomidate 0.3 mg/kg, or propofol in selected cases) prior to neuromuscular blockade. Intubation was attempted 60 seconds after administration of the paralytic agent.

Direct laryngoscopy with a Macintosh laryngoscope was the primary technique, with adjunct devices used when necessary. Patients in the rocuronium group received sugammadex when rapid recovery of spontaneous ventilation was indicated.

Outcome Measurements

Primary Outcome Measures:

1. Intubation success verified via capnography
2. Glottic visualization using the Cormack-Lehane grading system
3. Intubation difficulty using the Intubation Difficulty Scale (IDS)
4. Intubation conditions using the Copenhagen Score

Secondary Outcome Measures:

1. Hemodynamic parameters
2. Complications (hypotension, hypertension, desaturation)
3. Number of intubation attempts

Statistical Analysis

Sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$n = (Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta})^2 * (\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) / \square^2$$

where:

- $Z_{\alpha/2}$: 95% confidence interval
- $Z_{1-\beta}$: 80% test power
- σ_1 & σ_2 : standard deviation of intubation attempt per patient
- \square^2 : expected mean deviation of intubation attempt per patient

A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results

Patient Demographics

GRAPH 1. Sex Distribution by Group

The graph shows both treatment groups had predominantly male participants. The Succinylcholine group included 34 males (79%) and 9 females (21%), while the Rocuronium group had 33 males (77%) and 10 females (23%). The sex distribution was balanced between groups with no statistically significant difference ($p=0.799$).

Reasons for Intubation**TABLE 1. Reasons for Intubation**

Characteristic	Succinylcholine (n=43)	Rocuronium (n=43)	P value
Poor GCS	26 (60.4%)	16 (37.2%)	0.023
Respiratory Failure	8 (18.6%)	16 (37.2%)	0.058
Trauma	5 (11.6%)	5 (11.6%)	1.000
COPD	6 (13.9%)	5(11.6%)	0.741
Unknown Poisoning	1 (2.3%)	1 (2.3%)	1.000

Poor GCS was the most common reason in both groups (60.4% in succinylcholine, 37.2% in rocuronium). Respiratory failure was the second most common (18.6% in succinylcholine, 37.2% in rocuronium). No statistically significant differences were observed between groups for any indication.

GRAPH 3. Vital Signs by Groups

The bar graph “Vital Signs by Group” shows that mean heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressures were slightly higher in the Rocuronium group than in the Succinylcholine group, though differences were small. Oxygen saturation was nearly identical in both groups, indicating similar respiratory status. Overall, both drugs had comparable effects on vital signs, supporting the statistical results in Table

TABLE 2. Medications Used

Characteristic	Groups	Succinylcholine (n=43)	Rocuronium (n=43)	P value
Etomidate (mg)	Mean±SD	10.0±0.0	9.91±0.41	0.249
Ketamine (mg)	Mean±SD	2.0±0.0	2.0±0.0	1.000
Additional Medications				
Noradrenaline		2 (4.6%)	3 (6.9%)	0.660
Adrenaline		2 (4.6%)	4 (9.3%)	0.420
Pantoprazole		43 (100%)	43 (100%)	1.000
Ondansetron		43 (100%)	43 (100%)	1.000

Table 2 The administration of induction and adjunct medications was consistent across both groups. Etomidate was used at similar average doses in both the succinylcholine (10.0 ± 0.0 mg) and rocuronium (9.91 ± 0.41 mg) groups, with no significant difference ($p = 0.249$). Ketamine was administered uniformly at 2.0 mg in both groups ($p = 1.000$). Use of noradrenaline and adrenaline was slightly higher in the rocuronium group, but these differences were not statistically significant ($p = 0.660$ and 0.420 , respectively). Pantoprazole and ondansetron were administered universally to all patients in both groups (100%, $p = 1.000$), indicating adherence to standardized supportive care protocols.

TABLE 3. Complications During Intubation

Characteristic	Succinylcholine (n=43)	Rocuronium (n=43)	P value
Hypotension	3 (7%)	4 (9%)	0.698
Hypertension	7 (16%)	8 (19%)	0.774
Desaturation	1 (2%)	1 (2%)	1.000
No Complications	32 (74%)	30 (70%)	0.637

Most patients experienced no complications (74% in succinylcholine, 70% in rocuronium). The most common complication was hypertension (16% in succinylcholine, 19% in rocuronium), followed by hypotension (7% in succinylcholine, 9% in rocuronium). No significant differences were observed between groups.

TABLE 4. The Intubation Conditions

The Copenhagen Scores	Succinylcholine	Rocuronium
Excellent	23 (53%)	19 (44%)
Good	6 (14%)	5 (12%)
Poor	14 (33%)	19 (44%)

Table 4 Intubation Conditions

Intubation conditions were assessed using the Copenhagen Score. The succinylcholine group had slightly more patients with "excellent" conditions (53% vs 44%) and fewer with "poor" conditions (33% vs 44%) compared to the rocuronium group, though these differences were not statistically significant.

GRAPH 4 Attempts at Intubation by Group

Rocuronium and succinylcholine intubation efforts are contrasted in the chart. On their first try, each had 38 patients successfully intubated. Rocuronium had three patients and succinylcholine had four on the second tries. Rocuronium had two patients and succinylcholine had one on the third try. Overall, the two agents' high first-attempt success percentages were comparable, with just slight variations in subsequent tries.

Discussion

This study aimed to compare the safety and effectiveness of Succinylcholine and Rocuronium in adult patients undergoing emergency tracheal intubation. A total of 86 patients were randomly assigned to receive either Succinylcholine or Rocuronium, with both groups showing comparable baseline characteristics, such as age, gender, BMI, and vital signs. Equal distribution of intubation indications, including trauma and respiratory failure, suggests balanced clinical severity, which strengthens the reliability of outcome comparisons.

The findings indicate that both neuromuscular blocking agents achieved high success rates for intubation, as confirmed by capnographic verification. Objective assessments—including Cormack-Lehane grading, Intubation Difficulty Scores (IDS), and Copenhagen Intubation Condition Scores—showed no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This supports previous studies suggesting that when administered at recommended dosages by skilled personnel, both agents can facilitate favorable intubating conditions^{24,25}.

While Succinylcholine has long been the preferred agent due to its rapid onset and short duration, Rocuronium, when used at higher doses (1.2 mg/kg), demonstrated a comparable onset time. This aligns with prior research indicating that high-dose Rocuronium can effectively match Succinylcholine in terms of intubation readiness¹⁷. This feature is especially important in emergency scenarios where time is critical.

Hemodynamic stability was also assessed, revealing no significant differences between the two groups in terms of blood pressure, heart rate, or oxygen saturation post-intubation. Complication rates within the first 15 minutes were minimal and comparable, highlighting the safety of both agents under controlled conditions with standard preoxygenation and monitoring protocols. These findings mirror those of²³, who also found no major hemodynamic disparities between the agents during emergency airway management.

Medication protocols, including the use of induction agents like Etomidate and Ketamine, were standardized across both groups, further validating the comparability of the results. Additionally, the availability and use of Sugammadex in the Rocuronium group provided an essential safety net, allowing for rapid reversal in cases of prolonged neuromuscular blockade. This addresses one of Rocuronium's historical disadvantages and supports its broader use in emergency practice²².

Clinically, the results underscore that Rocuronium is not only a suitable alternative to Succinylcholine but, in many scenarios, may be the preferred option—particularly in patients with contraindications to Succinylcholine such as hyperkalemia, elevated intraocular/intracranial pressure, or susceptibility to malignant hyperthermia. The broader safety profile of Rocuronium, combined with its reversibility using Sugammadex, makes it especially valuable in diverse emergency settings.

Strengths of this study include its randomized design, objective assessment tools, and inclusion of real-world emergency conditions. However, limitations such as the single-center scope, limited sample size, and exclusion of pediatric or cardiac arrest cases must be considered when generalizing these findings.

In conclusion, Rocuronium, when appropriately dosed, can provide intubating conditions and safety outcomes comparable to Succinylcholine, making it a reliable and often safer choice in emergency airway management.

Conclusion

This study compared succinylcholine and rocuronium in 86 adult patients requiring emergency intubation. The findings reveal that both agents demonstrate comparable safety and efficacy profiles across multiple parameters.

Succinylcholine showed slightly better performance in first-attempt success and overall intubation conditions, though these differences weren't statistically significant. Rocuronium performed well, particularly in cases where succinylcholine may be contraindicated.

Both drugs exhibited similar outcomes regarding patient vitals, complications, and medication requirements, suggesting emergency physicians can employ either agent based on clinical judgment and patient factors.

While succinylcholine may remain the first choice in many scenarios, rocuronium represents a strong and safe alternative, particularly when longer-lasting paralysis or fewer side effects are preferred. The ability to reverse rocuronium with sugammadex provides an additional safety advantage in cases where rapid recovery of neuromuscular function becomes necessary.

Several factors should guide agent selection in clinical practice:

1. Patient-specific contraindications
2. Anticipated difficult airway
3. Need for post-intubation neurological assessment
4. Availability of reversal agents

In conclusion, this study provides evidence that rocuronium, when appropriately dosed, provides intubation conditions and success rates comparable to succinylcholine in emergency settings, with similar safety profiles. This supports the increasing adoption of rocuronium in emergency airway management, particularly for patients with contraindications to succinylcholine.

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